

**SONLI KETMA- KETLIKLAR VA ULARNING LIMITI BILAN BOG‘LIQ
TURLI MASALALAR**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ketma-ketlikning limiti bilan bog‘liq bir nechta murakkab masalalar o‘rganilgan.

Annotation. In the present article are considered some examples relating to limits of sequence.

Tayanch so‘zlar: Ketma-ketlik, chegaralangan ketma-ketlik, o‘sovchi (kamayuvchi) ketma-ketliklar, ketma-ketlikning limiti.

Key words: Sequence, bounded sequence, monotonic(decreasing) sequence, limit of the sequence.

Matematikada sonlar ketma ketligi va uning limitini hisoblash orqali ko‘plab murakkab masalalarni hal qilish mumkin. Biz ushbu maqolada sonlar ketma-ketligi, yaqinlashuvchi ketma-ketliklarni xossalari va ulardan foydalanib misol yechish uslubiyati keltirilgan. Buning uchun avvalo zarur ma’lumotlarni keltirib o‘tamiz.

Bizga $\{x_n\}$ -ketma-ketlik berilgan bo‘lsin.

1-ta‘rif: Ketma-ketlik yuqoridan (quyidan) chegaralangan deyiladi, agar shunday $M \in \mathbb{R}$ soni topilib, barcha $n \in \mathbb{N}$ larda $x_n \leq M$ ($x_n \geq M$) tengsizlik bajarilsa.

2-ta‘rif: $a \in \mathbb{R}$ soni $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlikning limiti deyiladi, agar har qanday $\varepsilon > 0$ son olinganda ham shunday $n_0(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$ son topilib, barcha $n > n_0(\varepsilon)$ larda

$$|x_n - a| < \varepsilon$$

tengsizlik bajarilsa.

$\{x_n\}$ -ketma-ketlikning limiti odatda $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = a$ kabi belgilanadi.

Agar ketma-ketlik chekli limitga ega bo‘lsa, u yaqinlashuvchi ketma-ketlik deyiladi.

3-ta‘rif: Agar ixtiyoriy a son va ixtiyoriy natural n_0 son olganda ham shunday musbat ε_0 soni va shunday natural $n > n_0$ son topilsaki,

$$|x_n - a| \geq \varepsilon_0$$

bo‘lsa, $\{x_n\}$ -ketma-ketlik limitga ega emas deb ataladi.

Agar ketma-ketlik limitga ega bo‘lmasa, u uzoqlashuvchi ketma-ketlik deyiladi.

Quyidan va yuqoridan chegaralangan ketma-ketlik chegaralangan ketma-ketlik deyiladi.

Endi ketma - ketlikning limiti tushinchasini keltiramiz.

Endi yaqinlashuvchi ketma-ketliklarning ba‘zi xossalari keltiramiz.

1^o. Agar x_n ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi va $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = a$ bo‘lib, $a > p$ ($a < q$) bo‘lsa, u holda ketma-ketlikning biror hadidan keyingi barcha hadlari ham p sonidan katta (q sonidan kichik) bo‘ladi.

2^o. Agar $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lsa, u chegaralangan bo‘ladi.

3^o. Agar $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lsa, uning limiti yagona bo‘ladi.

4^o. Agar $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik o‘sovchi (kamayuvchi) bo‘lib, yuqoridan (quyidan) chegaralangan bo‘lsa, u yaqinlashuvchi bo‘ladi.

5^o. Agar $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lib, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = a$ bo‘lsa, u holda istalgan $k \in N$ uchun $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_{n+k} = a$ bo‘ladi.

1-teorema. Agar $\{x_n\}$ va $\{y_n\}$ ketma-ketliklar yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lsa, $\{x_n \pm y_n\}$, $\{x_n \cdot y_n\}$ ketma-ketliklar ham yaqinlashuvchi va

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (x_n \pm y_n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n \pm \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (x_n \cdot y_n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n \cdot \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n$$

formula o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

2-teorema. Agar $\{x_n\}$ va $\{y_n\}$ ketma-ketliklar yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lib, $\forall n \in N$

uchun $y_n \neq 0$ va $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n \neq 0$ bo‘lsa, $\left\{ \frac{x_n}{y_n} \right\}$ ketma-ketlik ham yaqinlashuvchi

hamda

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{y_n} = \frac{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n}{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n}$$

formula o‘rinli bo‘ladi

Keltirilgan teoremlarni isbotini keltirmadik. Uni mustaqil ravishda [1-2] adabiyotlardan o‘rganishingizni tavsiya qilamiz.

1-misol. Ushbu

$$x_n = \frac{2024^n}{n!}$$

ketma-ketlikni chegaralanganligini isbotlang.

Isbot. Ma’lumki, $\frac{x_{n+1}}{x_n} = \frac{2024^{n+1}}{n+1!} \cdot \frac{n!}{2024^n} = \frac{2024}{n+1}$ tenglik o‘rinli.

Agar $n \geq 2023$ ($1 \leq n \leq 2023$) bo‘lsa, u holda $x_{n+1} \leq x_n$ ($x_{n+1} \geq x_n$) bo‘lib, $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik kamayuvchi (o‘sovchi) bo‘ladi. Bu esa istalgan $n \in \mathbb{N}$ larda

$0 \leq x_n \leq x_{2023} = \frac{2024^{2023}}{2023!}$ tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini bildiradi, ya’ni $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik chegaralangan.

Endi ketma-ketliklar nazariyasining eng ajoyib misollarini isbotlari bilan keltiramiz.

2-misol([3]). Ushbu

$$x_n = \sqrt{a + \sqrt{a + \sqrt{a + \dots + \sqrt{a}}}} \quad (a > 0)$$

ketma-ketlikning limitini toping.

Yechish: Har qanday $a > 0$ soni uchun $\sqrt{a + \sqrt{a}} > \sqrt{a}$ tengsizlikni o‘rinli bo‘lishini e’tiborga olsak, istalgan $n \in \mathbb{N}$ larda $x_{n+1} > x_n$ tengsizlik bajariladi, ya’ni $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik monoton o‘sovchi. $\sqrt{a + \sqrt{a}} < \sqrt{a} + 1$ va $\sqrt{a + \sqrt{a} + 1} < \sqrt{a} + 1$ tengsizliklardan foydalansak, istalgan $n \in \mathbb{N}$ larda $x_n < \sqrt{a} + 1$ tengsizlikka ega bo‘lamiz. 4⁰ xossaga ko‘ra $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = c$ mavjud va chekli. 5⁰ xossaga ko‘ra,

$$c = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_{n+1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{a + x_n} = \sqrt{a + c}.$$

$$c = \sqrt{a + c} \text{ tenglamadan } c \text{ ni topsak, } c = \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4a}}{2} \text{ bo‘ladi.}$$

3-misol. Agar $\{x_n\}$ ketma-ketlik $x_{n+1} - 2x_n + x_{n-1} = A$ ($n \geq 2, A \in \mathbb{R}$)

rekurrent munosabat orqali berilgan bo‘lsa, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{n^2}$ ni toping.

Yechish. Belgilash kiritamiz: $x_n - x_{n-1} = a_n$. Bundan $a_{n+1} - a_n = x_{n+1} - x_n - (x_n - x_{n-1}) = A$ bo‘ladi. Bu esa $\{a_n\}$ ketma-ketlik arifmetik progressiya ekanini bildiradi. Arifmetik progressiyani umumiy hadi formulasiga asosan $a_n = a_2 + (n - 2)A$ bo‘ladi.

$$x_n - x_{n-1} = a_2 + (n - 2)A$$

$$x_{n-1} - x_{n-2} = a_2 + (n - 3)A$$

.....

$$x_3 - x_2 = a_2 + A$$

Bu tengliklar hadlab qo‘shsak,

$$x_n - x_2 = (n - 2)a_2 + \frac{(n - 1)(n - 2)}{2} A$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Bu tenglikka asosan $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{n^2} = \frac{1}{2} A$ bo‘ladi.

4-misol. Istalgan $0 \leq x \leq 1$ uchun

$$\ln(1 + x) \geq x - \frac{1}{2}x^2$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini isbotlang.

Isbot. Funksiya kiritamiz:

$$f(x) = \ln(1 + x) - x + \frac{1}{2}x^2.$$

Uni hosilasini hisoblaymiz.

$$f'(x) = \frac{1}{1 + x} - 1 + x = \frac{1 - (1 - x^2)}{1 + x} = \frac{x^2}{1 + x}.$$

$f'(x) = \frac{x^2}{1 + x^2} \geq 0$ bo‘lgani uchun $f(x)$ funksiya $0 \leq x \leq 1$ da o‘svuchi va

$$f(x) \geq f(0) = 0$$

Bundan esa $\ln(1 + x) \geq x - \frac{1}{2}x^2$ tengsizlik kelib chiqadi.

5-misol. Istalgan $0 \leq \varepsilon \leq \frac{1}{4}$ da

$$f_\varepsilon(x) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)^{x+\varepsilon}, \quad x \geq 2$$

funksiyani monoton o‘svuchi bo‘lishini isbotlang.

Isbot. Funksiya hosilasini nomanfiy qiymatlar qabul qilishini isbotlaymiz.

$$f'_\varepsilon(x) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)^{x+\varepsilon} \left(\ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right) - \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{x} + \frac{1 - \varepsilon}{x + 1}\right) \right)$$

Agar $\ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right) \geq \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{2x^2}$, ($x \geq 2$) tengsizlikdan foydalansak,

$$f'_\varepsilon(x) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)^{x+\varepsilon} \left(\frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{2x^2} - \frac{\varepsilon}{x} - \frac{1-\varepsilon}{x+1}\right) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)^{x+\varepsilon} \left(\frac{2x(1-\varepsilon) - x - 1}{2x^2(x+1)}\right) =$$

$$= \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)^{x+\varepsilon} \left(\frac{(1-2\varepsilon)x - 1}{2x^2(1+x)}\right) \geq 0.$$

bo‘ladi. Bu esa $f_\varepsilon(x)$ funksiyani o‘svuchi ekanini bildiradi.

1 – natija. $x = n \in N, n \geq 2$ bo‘lsa,

$$x_n = \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n+\varepsilon}, \quad 0 \leq \varepsilon < \frac{1}{4}$$

ketma – ketlik monoton o‘svuchi.

2 – natija. Istalgan $0 \leq \varepsilon < \frac{1}{2}$ da

$$f_\varepsilon(x) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)^{x+\varepsilon}, \quad x \geq \frac{1}{1-2\varepsilon}$$

funksiya monoton o‘svuchi bo‘ladi.

3 – natija. Istalgan $\frac{1}{2} \leq \varepsilon \leq 1$ da

$$f_\varepsilon(x) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right)^{x+\varepsilon}, \quad x \geq 1$$

funksiya monoton kamayuvchi bo‘ladi.

Agar $\varepsilon = 1, x = n (n \in N)$ qilib tanlasak,

$$x_n = f_1(n) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n+1}$$

ketma – ketlik monoton kamayuvchi va quyidan chegaralangan ($x_n > 0, n \in N$).

Agar $\varepsilon = 0, x = n (n \in N)$ qilib tanlasak,

$$x_n = f_0(n) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n$$

ketma – ketlik monoton o‘svuchi va yuqoridan chegaralangan (Istalgan $n \in N$

larda $\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n < \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n+1} < \left(1 + \frac{1}{1}\right)^2 = 4$).

Shuning uchun 4^0 hossaga ko'ra $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n$ mavjud va chekli.

Ta'rif. Ushbu $x_n = \left\{ \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n \right\}$ ketma – ketlikning limiti e soni deb

ataladi:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n = e.$$

7 – misol. Ixtiyoriy $n \in N$ larda

$$n! \left(\frac{e}{n}\right)^n \geq \sqrt[4]{n} \quad (1)$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘lishini isbotlang.

Isbot. (1) tengsizlikni matematik induksiya metodi yordamida isbotlaymiz.

1. $n = 1$ va $n = 2$ holatlarda (1) tengsizlikni o‘rinli ekanini tekshirib ko‘rish mumkin.

2. (1) tengsizlik $n = k$ da ($k \geq 2$) da to‘g‘ri deb faraz qilamiz, ya‘ni

$$k! \left(\frac{e}{k}\right)^k \geq \sqrt[4]{k}, \quad k \geq 2$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli.

3. (1) tengsizlik $n = k + 1$ da ham o‘rinli bo‘linishini ko‘rsatamiz, ya‘ni

$$(k+1)! \left(\frac{e}{k+1}\right)^{k+1} \geq \sqrt[4]{k+1}.$$

Isbot.

$$\begin{aligned} (k+1)! \left(\frac{e}{k+1}\right)^{k+1} &= k! \left(\frac{e}{k}\right)^k \cdot \frac{e}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^k} = \frac{k! \left(\frac{e}{k}\right)^k}{\sqrt[4]{k}} \cdot \frac{e}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^{k+\frac{1}{4}}} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \cdot \sqrt[4]{k} = \\ &= \frac{k! \left(\frac{e}{k}\right)^k}{\sqrt[4]{k}} \cdot \frac{e}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^{k+\frac{1}{4}}} \cdot \sqrt[4]{k+1} \end{aligned}$$

Farazimizga ko‘ra istalgan $k \geq 2$ larda $k! \left(\frac{e}{k}\right)^k \geq \sqrt[4]{k}$ va 1-natijaga ko‘ra

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^{k+\frac{1}{4}} < e$$

tengsizlik o'rinli.

Demak,

$$k + 1 ! \left(\frac{e}{k + 1}\right)^{k+1} \geq \sqrt[4]{k + 1}.$$

To'la induksiya metodiga asosan (1) tengsizlik o'rinli.

4 – natija. Agar $x_n = n! \left(\frac{e}{n}\right)^n$ bo'lsa, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n! \left(\frac{e}{n}\right)^n = +\infty$ bo'ladi.

8-Misol. Agar $x_n = n! \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^n$, $a > 0$ bo'lsa, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n$ ni toping.

Yechish: Misolni bir nechta holatlarga ajratib yechamiz.

1) $0 < a < e$ bo'lsin.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_{n+1}}{x_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (n + 1)! \left(\frac{a}{n + 1}\right)^{n+1} \cdot \frac{1}{n! \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n} = \frac{a}{e} < 1$$

1^0 - xossaga ko'ra $\exists n_0 \in N$ son mavjudki, istalgan $n > n_0$ larda $\frac{x_n}{x_{n-1}} < \frac{a}{2}$.

Bundan $x_n < \left(\frac{a}{2}\right)^{n-n_0} \cdot x_{n_0}$ va $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = 0$.

2) $a > e$ bo'lsin. U holda $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_{n+1}}{x_n} = \frac{a}{e} > 1$ bo'lib, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = \infty$ bo'ladi.

3) $a = e$ holatda $n! \left(\frac{e}{n}\right)^n > \sqrt[4]{n}$ tengsizlikdan foydalansak

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n! \left(\frac{e}{n}\right)^n = +\infty$$

bo'ladi.

Demak, agar $0 < a < e$ ($a \geq e$) bo'lsa, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n! \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^n = 0$

($\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n! \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^n = +\infty$) bo'ladi.

Mustaqil yechish uchun masalar

1. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a^n}{n!}$ ni hisoblang.

2. $x_n = \underbrace{\sqrt[m]{a + \sqrt[m]{a + \dots + \sqrt[m]{a}}}}_{n \text{ ta}} \quad a > 0, m \in N, m \geq 2$

ketma-ketlikni yaqinlashuvchi ekanini isbotlang.

3. **([3])** $x_n = \sqrt{2\sqrt{3\sqrt{4\dots\sqrt{n}}}}$ ($n \geq 2$) ketma ketlikni

yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lishini isbotlang.

4. **([3]).** Agar $x_1 = 0, x_2 = 1, x_n = \frac{1}{2}$

$(x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}), (n = 2, 3, \dots)$ bo‘lsa, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n$ ni toping.

5. x_n ketma-ketlik berilgan bo‘lib,

$x_1 = 2015, x_{n+1} = \frac{1}{4 - 3x_n} (n \in N)$ bo‘lsa, u holda $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n$ ni toping.

6. x_n ketma-ketlik uchun

$x_0 = 2015, x_{n+1} = \frac{1}{2}(x_n + \frac{1}{x_n}), (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots)$

bo‘lsa, x_n ketma-ketlikni yaqinlashuvchiligini isbotlang.

7. x_n ketma-ketlikda $x_1 = a, x_2 = b$ va

$x_n = \frac{x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}}{2} (n \geq 3)$ bo‘lsa, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n$ ni toping.

8. Musbat hadli x_n, y_n ketma – ketlik berilgan bo‘lib,

$x_1 = a, y_1 = b, x_{n+1} = \sqrt{x_n y_n}, y_{n+1} = \frac{x_n + y_n}{2}$

bo‘lsa, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n$ va $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n$ ni toping.

9. Agar $x_n = \frac{n}{\sqrt[n]{n!}}$ bo‘lsa,

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = e$

bo‘lishini isbotlang.

10. **([3]).** Aytaylik,

$x_{n+1} = \lambda \cdot x_n + y_n, y_{n+1} = \lambda \cdot y_n - x_n (\lambda \neq 0)$ bo‘lsin. Agar

$$x_0^2 + y_0^2 \neq 0, \text{ bo'lsa, } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n \text{ ni toping.}$$

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